

Search for New Oral Hypoglycemic Agents. Part II. Synthesis of Some New Substituted Benzimidazoles

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Eighteen substituted benzimidazoles have been synthesised with a view to testing their hypoglycemic activity.

A survey of structures of the known antidiabetic compounds reveals that most of the important hypoglycemic agents carry a guanidine, urea, or a thiourea as their basic structural feature¹. The fact that the basic moiety is restored in benzimidazoles (as shown within block lines in formula I) coupled with the high antidiabetic activity exhibited by benzimidazole² prompted us to synthesise possible hypoglycemic agents derived from benzimidazole nucleus. In view of these considerations, eighteen new benzimidazole derivatives have been synthesised for evaluating their hypoglycemic activity.

In the present synthesis, *o*-phenylenediamine was condensed with formic, acetic, propionic^a, and butyric^a acids to yield the corresponding 2-substituted benzimidazoles (I: R₁=H, Me, Et, Prⁿ; R₂=H). These were treated with acid chlorides to yield the required substituted benzimidazoles.

The m.p., yields, and analysis, etc. of the benzimidazoles represented by formula (I) are recorded in Table I.

EXPERIMENTAL

A mixture of 2-*n*-alkylbenzimidazoles (0.25*M*), chloride of *p*-methylphenylsulphonyl, α - and β -naphthalenesulphonyl, *p*-acetaminophenylsulphonyl or dichloroacetyl (0.05*M* each), and anhydrous potassium carbonate (0.25*M*) in absolute ethanol (15 ml) was refluxed on a water bath for 24 hours under anhydrous condition. The substituted benzimidazoles were extracted with hot ethanol and recrystallised from the same solvent (hot).

1. Tiwari and Swaroop, *this Journal*, 1961, 38, 245.

2. Okamoto *et al.*, *Tohoku J. Expt. Med.*, 1955, 61, suppl. 3-116, pp. 36-61.

TABLE I

R ₂ .	M.P.	%Yield.	Formula.	% Nitrogen.	
				Found.	Reqd.
R ₁ = H.					
CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄ SO ₂	246°	74	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ O ₂ N ₂ S	10.10	10.30
C ₁₀ H ₇ SO ₂	161°	69	C ₁₇ H ₁₂ O ₂ N ₂ S	9.08	9.21
C ₁₀ H ₇ SO ₂	272°	72	C ₁₇ H ₁₂ O ₂ N ₂ S	9.10	9.21
Cl ₂ CHCO	178°	76	C ₉ H ₆ ON ₂ Cl ₂	12.18	12.3
R ₁ = Me.					
CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄ SO ₂	224°	65	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₂ S	9.64	9.79
C ₁₀ H ₇ SO ₂	253°	61	C ₁₈ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₂ S	8.61	8.70
C ₁₀ H ₇ SO ₂	204°	63	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₂ S	8.63	8.70
Cl ₂ CHCO	184°	68	C ₁₀ H ₈ ON ₂ Cl ₂	11.30	11.80
R ₁ = Et.					
CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄ SO ₂	201°	78	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₂ S	9.13	9.24
C ₁₀ H ₇ SO ₂	226°	74	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₂ S	8.28	8.33
C ₁₀ H ₇ SO ₂	214°	76	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₂ S	8.24	8.33
CH ₃ CONHC ₆ H ₄ SO ₂	154°	64	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ O ₃ N ₂ S	12.15	12.25
Cl ₂ CHCO	183°	69	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ ON ₂ Cl ₂	10.86	10.90
R ₁ = Pr ⁿ .					
CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄ SO ₂	282°	57	C ₁₇ H ₁₈ O ₂ N ₂ S	8.86	8.92
C ₁₀ H ₇ SO ₂	231°	56	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ O ₂ N ₂ S	7.94	8.04
C ₁₀ H ₇ SO ₂	272°	58	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ O ₂ N ₂ S	7.89	8.04
CH ₃ CONHC ₆ H ₄ SO ₂	254°	62	C ₁₈ H ₁₉ O ₃ N ₂ S	11.73	11.80
Cl ₂ CHCO	191°	71	C ₁₂ H ₁₂ ON ₂ Cl ₂	10.31	10.35

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